

Book of Abstracts

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Book of Abstracts

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Effects of laser power and feeder speed on samples prepared by laser morphing in the Everglass project

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ABSTRACT

Glass can be considered as a key material for achieving a carbon-free future, but current recycling technologies are limited, especially for other types of glass such as borosilicate glass, optical glass and display glass. The Everglass project addresses this challenge by using laser-induced morphing to recycle borosilicate glass waste into laboratory-scale prototypes. The study investigates the influence of laser morphology parameters—such as laser power and feeder rotor speed—on optical and confocal microscopy results, transmittance, XRD patterns, and SEM-EDS analysis. The melting and feeding of the glass were carried out alternately in both directions. Optical microscopy on cross section revealed bubbles forming predominantly during movement in one direction (Fig.1). Although it is not yet possible to perfectly align the laser and feeder along a single axis—resulting in surface roughness on one side of the sample— diffraction data confirm that both sides of the samples maintain an amorphous structure, with no detectable crystalline phases despite variations in laser power and feeder rotor speed (Fig.2).

Fig.1: Cross-sections of samples processed with varying laser power and feeder rotor speed., A–C: Samples produced with different laser power (A: 30 W – lowest, B: 70 W – medium, C: 90 W – highest), D–E: Samples produced with different feeder rotor speeds (D: 25 rpm – lowest, E: 55 rpm – highest)

Fig.2: XRD record of the sample prepared by laser-induced morphing

Keywords: borosilicate glass system, glass laser morphology object, glass recycling, laser power, feeder rotor speed

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Surface modifications of zirconia-based ceramics for dental applications: in vitro cytotoxicity and proliferation using MG63 cells

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates surface modifications of 3Y-TZP ceramics to improve bone tissue integration during the early osseointegration stage. Three treatments, sandblasting, acid etching, and their combination, were applied to sintered and polished 3Y-TZP samples. Acid etching was performed using either 40% hydrofluoric acid with 52.5% nitric acid or a mixture of 48% tetrafluoroboric acid, 63% nitric acid, and 36% hydrochloric acid. Samples were sandblasted with 25–177 µm corundum particles. In vitro tests with MG-63 osteoblast cells demonstrated that sandblasting significantly enhanced cell proliferation, achieving the highest viability after 10 days. All tested groups showed no significant cytotoxic effects on cell viability. The polished control and the combined treatment (sandblasting with hydrofluoric and nitric acid etching) showed the highest cell viability after 24 hours, while the tetrafluoroboric acid-etched group displayed the lowest. Sandblasting and combined treatments with etching are promising surface modifications, however, the combined procedure requires further optimization.

Keywords: 3Y-TZP, surface modification, osseointegration, surface roughness, wettability, cell proliferation, cytotoxicity

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Tailoring 58S Sol-Gel Coatings for Biodegradable Magnesium Implants

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on the development of durable and bioactive coatings for magnesium alloys, particularly AZ31B, used in orthopaedic implants. This study aims to investigate the application of 58S bioactive glass coatings modified with silica precursors such as GPTMS and MTES in specified ratios with TEOS to increase the efficacy of coatings for controlled degradation. This study highlights the difficulties presented by the thermal strains imposed by the ceramic layer on the sol-gel coating during the curing process, particularly for the PEO-modified alloy. The PEO method produces a porous, oxide-dense surface that enhances coating adherence and bioactivity. The bioactive layer applied via the 58S sol-gel coating undergoes stress during the curing process, increasing the risk of delamination or cracking. This study compares the ability of the silica precursors GPTMS and MTES to increase the flexibility and adherence of the coating through the formation of hybrid silica networks. The ratios of these precursors with TEOS are optimised to achieve a balance between coating stability and bioactivity. Characterisation techniques, including SEM, FTIR, and electrochemical studies, reveal that optimised sol-gel coatings display superior bioactivity, regulated degradation, and improved mechanical stability. The thermal stress of the ceramic layer on the sol-gel during curing significantly affects the coating's microstructure and adherence, rendering the selection and proportion of silica precursors essential for attaining a robust and efficient bioactive coating. These results indicate that modified 58S sol-gel coatings with optimum precursor ratios can substantially enhance the durability and biological efficacy of magnesium-based implants, offering a new avenue for enhanced biodegradable biomedical materials. This work enhances the understanding of the interactions among coating composition, curing stress, and biofunctionality in magnesium implant coating technologies.

Keywords: Biodegradability; Biomedical application; Magnesium alloys; Sol-gel.

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Hot corrosion of YSZ and Gd₂Zr₂O₇/YSZ thermal barrier coatings in Na₂SO₄ + V₂O₅ molten salt

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ABSTRACT

Thermal barrier coatings (TBCs) are currently used in modern gas turbines and diesel engines to provide thermal insulation against hot gases and to improve the performance and efficiency of these machines [1]. The use of TBCs is expected to increase their operating temperature or eliminate the need for cooling. Therefore, there is an increasing demand to develop new TBC materials with long lifetimes, low thermal conductivity and high temperature resistance. Recent studies have proposed gadolinium zirconate (Gd₂Zr₂O₇) as a promising TBC material [2, 3]. Compared with yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ), the most commonly used TBC material, Gd₂Zr₂O₇ provides more attractive properties, such as lower thermal conductivity, improved sintering resistance, and high phase stability at temperatures >1500 °C. Therefore, in this work, single-layer YSZ and double-layer Gd₂Zr₂O₇/YSZ TBC systems were developed using air plasma spraying (APS). The main goal of this study was to evaluate their hot corrosion resistance in the presence of Na₂SO₄+V₂O₅ molten salt at 950 °C. The resulting microstructural changes were evaluated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The surfaces of the hot corroded samples were also analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) to identify corrosion products formed due to interaction with the molten salt. The results showed that corrosion mechanism in single-layer YSZ coating was initiated by migration of the molten salt through micro-cracks and open pores and its reaction with the zirconia stabilizer (Y₂O₃). This led to the formation of YVO₄ corrosion products and the transformation of tetragonal ZrO₂ to monoclinic ZrO₂. For the double-layer Gd₂Zr₂O₇/YSZ coating, the molten salt reacted with Gd₂Zr₂O₇ to form GdVO₄ and m-ZrO₂. Although the molten salt infiltrated the Gd₂Zr₂O₇ top layer, the production of GdVO₄ consumed most of the corrosive V₂O₅, thus delaying molten salt penetration into the YSZ interlayer and the formation of YVO₄ crystals. Therefore, it can be concluded that the double-layer Gd₂Zr₂O₇/YSZ system exhibits better hot corrosion resistance.

Keywords: gadolinium zirconate, hot corrosion, thermal barrier coatings, yttria-stabilized zirconia

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Microstructure-Driven Thermal Conductivity Modeling of 8YSZ Thermal Barrier Coatings

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ABSTRACT

This work investigates the thermal conductivity behavior of plasma-sprayed 8YSZ thermal barrier coatings using a combination of experimental measurements, image-based modeling and analytical calculation. High-resolution SEM images of the coating microstructure of four different porosities were processed through thresholding, pixelation and meshing to obtain machine readable microstructures. The pixelated microstructures were directly used for finite element simulations in ANSYS APDL. In parallel, a six-phase analytical model was developed in Python, extending on the traditional Bruggeman two-phase approach to include N- type of defect types using an iterative averaging scheme. For each porosity level, at least five different micrographs from distinct regions were analyzed. Computed non-dimensional thermal conductivities show good agreement with experimental data at lower to moderate porosities but deviate at higher porosity levels. This integrated approach provides a predictive tool for rationally designing next-generation TBCs with tailored thermal properties that are required for high temperature environments. Moreover, this approach will streamline the optimization of process parameters for deposition of TBCs, utilizing the simulation-based strategy for determining required coating thickness and porosity to meet explicit thermal conductivity values defined by industries.

Keywords: Image based modelling, Finite element analysis, plasma spraying, 8YSZ, thermal barrier coating

Acknowledgement:

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The Role of Nitrogen Incorporation in Tailoring the Structure and Properties of ZnO Thin Films Deposited by Magnetron Sputtering Technology

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ABSTRACT

Zinc oxide (ZnO) is widely used in antireflective coatings and optical devices due to its excellent transparency, chemical stability, and tunable electronic properties. Nitrogen-doped zinc oxide (N-ZnO) thin films were deposited on glass substrates by magnetron sputtering using both Zn–Sn (10Sn–90Zn) and Al-doped ZnO (AZO) targets. Different nitrogen gas (N₂) flow rates were introduced during deposition to investigate the influence of nitrogen incorporation on film structure and surface properties. The thin films were characterized using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), X-ray diffraction (XRD), UV–visible spectroscopy, drop shape analysis, and scratch testing. XPS confirmed successful nitrogen incorporation within the ZnO lattice. XRD analysis revealed that nitrogen doping reduced the crystallinity. Optical measurements showed that all films exhibited high transparency, which further improved after post-deposition heat treatment. AFM and drop shape analysis indicated that nitrogen doping decreased surface roughness and increased hydrophobicity. Scratch tests demonstrated improved adhesion of N-ZnO films to glass substrates for both targets compared to undoped ZnO. These findings highlight that controlled nitrogen doping and appropriate heat treatment can tailor the microstructural, optical, and mechanical properties of ZnO-based films, making them promising candidates for optoelectronic and protective coating applications.

Keywords: antireflective, hydrophobicity, magnetron sputtering, nitrogen, scratch resistance.

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Can Additive Manufacturing (AM) be a Sustainable and Economically Feasible Route for Recycling and Upcycling Waste Materials?

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ABSTRACT

The United Nations' 2030 Agenda emphasizes Goal 12, which advocates sustainable management of resources, reduction of waste, and responsible treatment of by-products. Central to this goal is the adoption of circular economic strategies that transform waste and discarded materials, often bound for landfills, into valuable resources and feedstocks. A truly sustainable, closed-loop manufacturing system can be achieved when waste materials are recycled/upcycled into high-value products with feasible processability, while maintaining cost-effectiveness, energy efficiency, and practical applicability. In this context, Additive Manufacturing (AM), commonly known as 3D printing, offers a promising pathway toward sustainable material utilization by enabling the direct reuse of waste resources to fabricate high-performance, custom-designed 3D components. Despite its potential, the integration of waste materials, particularly glass and ceramics, into AM technologies remains in its early stages. This lecture will explore recent advancements in waste glass upcycling enabled by Industry 4.0 technologies, including 3D printing, specifically VAT photopolymerization and Binder Jetting, alongside 3D modeling and artificial intelligence. Emphasis will be placed on how these strategies not only address process effectiveness but also expand the design space for digital manufacturing in next-generation materials innovation. This discussion will also highlight the broad application potential of this approach across sectors such as construction, architectural components, photocatalysis, and filtration.

Keywords: Additive manufacturing, Waste glass, VAT Photopolymerization, Binder Jetting, 3D modeling

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Towards Sustainability: Aqueous Solution Ion Exchange (AS-IET) for Glass Strengthening

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ABSTRACT

This study systematically introduces and evaluates a sustainable aqueous solution ion-exchange treatment (AS-IET) as a greener, safer, and more cost-effective alternative to the conventional molten salt ion-exchange treatment (MS-IET) for strengthening borosilicate pharmaceutical glass vials (PGVs). Strengthening PGVs remains a major challenge in the pharmaceutical packaging industry, particularly during storage, transportation, and the rigorous mechanical stresses encountered on high-speed filling and capping lines. The AS-IET process employs carefully optimized aqueous potassium nitrate (KNO₃) solutions of varying concentrations to achieve a homogeneous coating on both the inner and outer vial surfaces, followed by direct heat treatment (DHT) at 400 °C, 450 °C, and 500 °C for durations of 2, 12, and 24 hours. This process effectively enhances the mechanical strength of borosilicate glass by generating a robust compressive stress layer on the surface, nearly doubling its resistance to crushing loads with increasing temperature and duration, while maintaining optical transparency, color, and functional integrity.

Untreated PGVs exhibited baseline crushing loads of 1375 N for PGV-A and 1669 N for PGV-B. After AS-IET at 500 °C for 2 hours, the values increased to 1797 N and 2059 N, showing improvements of 30.76 % and 23.38 %, respectively. Under the same conditions, MS-IET achieved 1932 N (PGV-A) and 2247 N (PGV-B), corresponding to 40.58 % and 34.58 % increases. Extending AS-IET to 24 hours at 500 °C further raised the crushing loads to 2481 N and 2815 N, representing 80.36 % and 68.66 % improvements over the untreated samples. These results demonstrate the strong influence of prolonged thermal diffusion on the ion mobility and compressive layer formation, confirming AS-IET's capability to achieve significant strengthening without molten salts or introduce any liquid into the furnace. AS-IET not only improves mechanical strength but also enhances chemical durability by reducing Na⁺ and K⁺ leaching. Treated vials showed no radial cracks after indentation at higher treatment temperatures and durations, confirming the development of effective surface compressive stresses. EDS analysis verified true ion exchange, showing increased K and reduced Na near the surface. Unlike MS-IET, AS-IET requires no salt melting, uses less energy, avoids corrosion and waste, and offers a scalable, eco-efficient route to improve borosilicate pharmaceutical glass.

Keywords: Aqueous Solution Ion Exchange (AS-IET), Mechanical and Chemical Durability, Borosilicate Glass Strengthening, Molten Salt Ion Exchange (MS-IET), Pharmaceutical Packaging, Sustainable Glass Processing.

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Fused Deposition Modelling and Autodesk Inventor: Principles and advanced Applications

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ABSTRACT

Fused deposition modelling (FDM) is an advanced additive manufacturing technique used for producing ceramics, metals, and composite materials. Its ease of use, prototyping accuracy, and low operational cost make it one of the most widely adopted additive manufacturing methods. The nozzle diameter, typically ranging from 0.25 to 0.8 mm, significantly influences printing accuracy, with achievable feature sizes varying approximately from 150 to 600 μm depending on the nozzle size and the particle size of the additives within the filament. The fabrication process begins with generating a digital model in 3D design software such as Autodesk Inventor, followed by slicing the model into a series of layers for printing. Autodesk Inventor is extensively used for parametric modelling and simulation of complex three-dimensional structures, enabling the creation of highly detailed geometries suitable for additive manufacturing, including components with intricate internal features. In addition to its advanced modelling capabilities, the software incorporates comprehensive finite element analysis tools that evaluate the mechanical behaviour of designed components under various loading conditions. These simulations can be performed using a broad range of material models, including metals, glass, ceramics, and polymers, facilitating accurate predictions of structural performance. Moreover, Autodesk Inventor supports the assembly of individual parts into complete systems, providing realistic visualizations of the final manufactured product and enabling assessment of potential design improvements prior to fabrication. The main advanced applications of FDM include the fabrication of filters, catalytic reactors, bioceramic implants, and functional mechanical metal components.

Keywords: Fused deposition modelling, autodesk inventor, CAD, 3D printing, stress analysis

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From 3D-printed glass to nanoporous materials: shaping a cleaner future

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, ceramic composites have gained significant attention due to their remarkable properties, such as high chemical resistance and thermal stability. However, traditional fabrication methods often face challenges in achieving precise control over material properties and complex geometries. Additive manufacturing is a transformative technology enabling the production of complex three-dimensional structures that preserve or enhance the raw material properties.

Recent advances in 3D printing have opened new possibilities for creating multifunctional materials that can effectively host and remove hazardous contaminants. The challenge lies in understanding how specific manufacturing techniques and structural features influence microstructural properties.

This study explores the feasibility of producing nanoporous high-silica glass structures using vat photopolymerization (VPP) of ceramics. A sodium-borosilicate glass with high thermal stability and resistance to chemical attack was prepared and used as a starting material. A unique feature of this glass is its ability to undergo phase separation, which was exploited by performing debinding and phase-separation treatments simultaneously. Various leaching treatments were tested to achieve tailored porosity.

This study included characterization of the rheological properties and photo reactivity of the ceramic suspensions, as well as the density and porosity of the green bodies and sintered parts. Additionally, thermogravimetric analysis and scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy, were conducted to examine the microstructural properties. Finally, the nanoporous 3D-printed structures were evaluated for their wastewater treatment effectiveness by assessing their ability to remove methylene blue.

Keywords: 3D glass structures, methylene blue, nanoporous structures, phase separation. vat polymerization.

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Upgrading an FDM 3D Printer into a versatile and effective direct ink writing system

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ABSTRACT

Additive manufacturing has gained significant attention for its versatility and ability to fabricate complex geometries with high precision. Among extrusion-based approaches, Direct Ink Writing (DIW) stands out for its capability to process viscous slurries and pastes through controlled extrusion. Conventional DIW systems typically rely on pneumatic, piston, or screw-driven mechanisms. Although pneumatic extrusion offers a simple and lightweight setup suitable for low-viscosity inks, it lacks precise flow-rate control, making it unsuitable for highly viscous, time-dependent materials. In contrast, stepper motor-driven extrusion provides accurate, G-code-controlled deposition synchronized with print head motion, enabling consistent material delivery.

In this study, a commercial Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) printer was successfully modified into a DIW system. After evaluating pneumatic-based and stepper motor extruder head configurations, an optimized stepper motor-driven syringe extruder was developed, enabling precise and consistent deposition of viscoelastic paste systems. Printing parameters, including extrusion rate, path continuity, and travel speed, were modeled and optimized in Rhino coupled with Grasshopper to generate an efficient G-code suitable for continuous printing paths and improve geometric accuracy. The system was validated through the high-precision printing of waste glass-based alkali-activated pastes exhibiting time-dependent viscosity and variable rheological behavior. Furthermore, the setup was adapted for multimaterial extrusion using custom-designed nozzles for core-shell and multilayer deposition. This work demonstrates a cost-effective and adaptable approach for converting conventional FDM printers into DIW platforms, integrating digital design, rheology control, and automated process management to achieve accurate and reliable printing of complex, highly viscous materials.

Keywords: Additive manufacturing, design, direct ink writing, extrusion.

Acknowledgement: - This paper is part of the dissemination activities of the project APVV-23-0352.

LiREF₄@LiRE'F₄ Core-Shell Nanoplatfom towards Quantum dot-integrated Heterostructures

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ABSTRACT

This study presents the synthesis and preliminary characterisation of ultrasmall (~ 10 nm) and ~ 20 nm LiREF₄ (RE = Lu, Tb, Yb) nanoparticles (NPs), engineered as a heterostructure platform for integration with InP/ZnS quantum dots (QDs) to facilitate multiplexing luminescence nanomaterials. The core nanoparticles were synthesized via solvothermal decomposition at 285–310 °C using oleic acid (OA) as the capping ligand. Subsequently, LiRE'F₄ (RE' = Gd, Yb) shells were epitaxially grown on the cores by a similar solvothermal process. Optimising the ligand-to-precursor ratio was essential for the regulation of the nucleation and development of the nanoparticles. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to prove the effective surface capping by OA. This was notably evident in the disappearance of the 1707 cm⁻¹ peak, which corresponds to the carboxyl group, suggesting effective conjugation of COO⁻ groups with the RE³⁺ present on the nanoparticle surface, a critical factor in the maintenance of colloidal stability. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) revealed well-dispersed LiREF₄ nanoparticles at 2 different sizes: ~ 20 nm and below 10 nm, while high-resolution TEM (HRTEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses unequivocally verified the crystalline phase and lattice structure of tetragonal LiLuF₄ (JCPDS No. 027–1251, *I*4_{1/a}, *a* = *b* = 5.126, *c* = 10.539). Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) quantified the OA coverage at ~ 3 –4 molecules/nm², which enabled stability of the ~ 20 nm metastable phase of LiREF₄. Due to the steric effect, reducing the OA coverage below 2 molecules/nm² led to out-of-control particle growth, agglomeration and a tendency to phase separation into LiF and REF₃, demonstrating the critical role of ligand density in nanoparticle size and phase control. This study is in progress and involves the optimisation of the LiRE'F₄ shell, the synthesis and integration of InP/ZnS QDs with the LiREF₄:Tb/Yb NPs, and the assessment of optical properties through photoluminescence (PL) and upconversion measurements. The objective is to develop advanced heterostructure luminescent nanomaterials which improve multiplexed optical applications in sensing, imaging, and anticounterfeiting by integrating the size-tunable broadband emission of quantum dots with the long-lived emission and efficient energy transfer of rare-earth-doped hosts.

Keywords: LiREF₄ nanoparticles, nano-heterostructure, quantum dots, Terbium, upconversion luminescence.

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Tuning the Properties of Mesoporous Bioactive Glass Nanoparticles through Calcium Nitrate Addition Timing

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ABSTRACT

Mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles (MBGNPs) are promising materials for biomedical applications owing to their large pore volume, high porosity, and specific surface area. In addition, MBGNPs exhibit superior bioactivity, and can be utilized for the loading of biological molecules such as growth factors and enzymes. The microemulsion-assisted sol–gel method is a common synthesis route for incorporating metallic ions into MBGNPs [1]. In this study, MBGNPs were synthesized using the microemulsion-assisted sol–gel method, which employs cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) as a surfactant to establish the mesoporous structure under basic conditions. Hydrophobic ethyl acetate (EA) molecules are added to the aqueous CTAB solution, where the CTAB micelles self-assemble with EA to form oil-in-water microemulsion droplets. It has been demonstrated that the textural properties of MBGNPs can be tuned by varying the concentration of CTAB and aqueous ammonia [1]. Furthermore, it has been reported that the timing of calcium nitrate addition can modify the properties of bioactive glass nanoparticles [2] and it is expected that this parameter could also affect the properties of MBGNPs. This study investigates the effect of calcium nitrate addition timing on the textural and structural properties with biocompatibilities of MBGNPs. Morphological and textural properties were analyzed with FESEM, HR-TEM, N₂ adsorption–desorption, and SAXS/USAXS. Structural characterization was complemented by FTIR and MAS-NMR. Indirect *in vitro* cytocompatibility was assessed with human osteosarcoma MG-63 cells. The results show that varying the timing of calcium nitrate addition is an effective strategy for tailoring the textural properties of MBGNPs.

Keywords: Calcium nitrate tetrahydrate, Mesoporous bioactive nanoparticles

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Bismuth-containing bioactive glasses: silicate and borate networks for bioactive powders to be used in coatings deposition

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ABSTRACT

The addition of ions to the structure of well-known bioactive glasses (BG) is becoming a matter of interest for the so-called *ionic medicine* in these glasses. Such modifications seek to improve or include additional features to BG, and currently, an important number of different elements have been considered and researched for this purpose. Bismuth has emerged as a promising candidate for the modification of bioactive glasses, due to its antibacterial, radiation shielding, and radiopacity features in the glass while keeping the in-situ bioactivity and biocompatibility of the amorphous material. In the current contribution, we present the results of a comparison between bismuth-containing silicate 45S5 and borate 13-93B3 bioactive glasses as interesting candidates to be used in the functionalization of medical-grade surfaces. This initiative is part of the results of the RADIOBIOCOATS project from the Slovak Recovery and Resilience Plan supported by the European Union. We investigated the structural, thermal, chemical, bioactive, antibacterial, and cell viability features of the melt and quenched 45S5 and 13-93B3 glasses with progressive additions of Bi₂O₃. The results indicated that both types of glasses with additions among 7-10 wt. % of Bi₂O₃ showed no toxic effects on MG-63 osteoblast-like cells while keeping the glass structural, bioactive, and thermal features. It was proven that the addition of bismuth oxide improves the glass's contrast in radiographic images (radiopacity) and antibacterial activity. Finally, we showed the feasibility of using both kinds of bismuth-containing bioactive glasses as a promising material to functionalize medical-grade metallic substrates by deposition techniques as Atmospheric Plasma Spray and Electrophoretic Deposition (EPD)

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Ionic medicine: Impact of various ions on osteogenesis.

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ABSTRACT

Ionic medicine, the concept of guiding cellular behavior through controlled ionic cues, represents an emerging frontier in bone tissue regeneration. Mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles (MBGNs) provide a versatile platform for the tailored release of biologically active ions, enabling precise modulation of cell signaling pathways relevant to osteogenesis. This project aims to investigate how MBGNs based on silica, doped with calcia, magnesium, and cerium, influence the biogenesis and osteoinductive function of cell-derived exosomes.

The proposed work focuses on synthesizing and characterizing ion-doped MBGNs with controlled mesoporosity and defined dissolution profiles, followed by evaluating their interaction with osteoprogenitor cells¹. Particular attention will be given to how specific ions—or their synergistic combinations—affect exosome production, molecular cargo loading, and the exosomes' capacity to enhance osteogenic differentiation. Magnesium and calcium ions are anticipated to support matrix mineralization pathways, silica to promote early osteogenic signaling, and cerium to modulate oxidative balance and potentially improve exosome stability and regenerative efficacy²⁻⁴.

By integrating materials engineering with extracellular vesicle biology, this research seeks to establish a mechanistic understanding of how ionic dissolution products can reprogram cell secretory behavior toward pro-osteogenic outcomes⁵⁻⁶. Ultimately, the study aims to define design principles for next-generation MBGNs that can stimulate therapeutic exosomes for acellular bone regeneration strategies. This forward-looking approach positions ionic medicine as a promising avenue for advancing osteogenic therapies through synergistic material–cell communication.

Keywords: mesoporous silica nanoparticles, therapeutic ions, exosomes

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Smart pH-Triggered Antibacterial Silica for Oral Infection Control

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ABSTRACT

Mesoporous silica (MS) materials are widely studied for drug delivery due to their high surface area, tunable pore architecture, and straightforward functionalization. A new hybrid MS with a monomodal pore size distribution was synthesized using Surfactant PolyIon Complex (SPIC) micelles formed by electrostatic complexation of the cationic antimicrobial surfactant cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC) and a double hydrophilic block copolymer (PAA-b-PEOGA). The resulting material combines stable PEOGA anchoring within the silica matrix and CPC retained inside mesopores, enabling pH-responsive release typical for oral pathological microenvironments. The microbiological evaluation focused on four clinically relevant oral pathogens, representing both aerobic (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*) and anaerobic (*Streptococcus mutans*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*) species. Antibacterial activity was assessed using standardized NCCLS M7 methodology to determine minimal inhibitory (MIC) and minimal bactericidal concentrations, complemented by metabolic assays to monitor bacterial growth inhibition. The hybrid MS exhibited MIC values in the range of 2–32 µg/mL under standard conditions, demonstrating broad and potent antibacterial activity.

To examine pH-triggered CPC release under biologically relevant conditions, the assay was modified using a medium supporting natural acidification. At physiological pH (7.4), MIC values ranged from 32–64 µg/mL. Upon acidification to pH 5.5, a marked potentiation of antibacterial activity was observed, most notably in *S. mutans* (MIC decrease from 64 to 8 µg/mL) and *S. aureus* (from 64 to 32 µg/mL), indicating effective CPC liberation in acidic environments characteristic of cariogenic biofilms.

These findings confirm that SPIC-templated hybrid MS acts as an efficient pH-responsive antimicrobial system with strong inhibitory effects against key oral pathogens, underscoring its suitability for targeted dental drug delivery applications.

Keywords: hybrid mesoporous silica material; surfactant polyion complex micelles; antimicrobial properties; pH-stimuli;

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Bioactive magnetic composite sponges, integrating controlled simvastatin delivery, magnetic hyperthermia and shape recovery

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ABSTRACT

Current challenging times have significantly impacted all aspects of human life, including those related to quality of life and a healthy lifestyle, which have been severely affected. As a result, there is an increasing number of cases related to a variety of medical disorders or conditions, which not only increase in complexity but also generate a growing demand for specialized treatments. These treatments must address medical challenges from multiple angles, providing simultaneous therapeutic functions to minimize the adverse and invasive effects that are often associated with conventional, multi-step therapies. In this sense, the development of novel systems with multifunctional, biocompatible, and bioactive properties, capable of withstanding certain mechanical demands, is highly desirable.

In this work, we developed multifunctional hybrid crosslinked sponges composed of chitosan and κ -carrageenan that incorporate a high content (46 wt% respect to polysaccharides) of inorganic particles in form of magnetic SBA-15/Fe₃O₄ composites and nano-sized hydroxyapatite crystals. Novel magnetic sponges were able to produce heat through magnetic hyperthermia, generating different reactions, from mild heat to cell ablation, modulated by both the type of magnetic system and the frequency applied using a magnetic field of 28 mT. The presence of SBA-15/Fe₃O₄ particles provided a controlled release of simvastatin for extended periods, in addition to conferring the entire sponge a highly porous and interconnected structure with a remarkably rough surface. Furthermore, the sponges recovered their shape after compression under wet conditions. High cell viability was observed when tested in direct contact with MG63 cells, with no cytotoxic response occurring, highlighting the potential of these multifunctional sponges for biomedical applications.

Keywords: Bioactive magnetic sponges, Drug delivery, Hydroxyapatite, Magnetic hyperthermia, Multifunctional hybrid systems, SBA-15/Fe₃O₄ composites, Shape recovery.

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Preliminary Study on DLP Manufacturing of 1393B3 Borate Bioactive Glass Scaffolds with Cortical and Cancellous Bone–Mimicking Designs

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ABSTRACT

In our preliminary work, 1393B3 borate bioactive glass (BG) scaffolds were successfully fabricated using additive manufacturing technology, particularly the Digital Light Processing (DLP) technique. After low-temperature sintering at 600 °C, the scaffolds exhibited excellent densification while maintaining their amorphous structure. Furthermore, the feasibility of multi-material printing by combining 1393B3 borate bioactive glass with nanoparticles was demonstrated.

In the present study, computer-aided design (CAD) was employed to construct several geometries mimicking the porous architectures of natural cortical and cancellous bone. These designs were subsequently fabricated as solid 1393B3 borate bioactive glass scaffolds via DLP printing.

During the fabrication process, two major challenges were encountered. The first was the detachment of printed objects with complex geometries from the build platform. The second was the failure of highly delicate structures due to the insufficient mechanical stability of thin trabecula. The detachment issue was mitigated by optimizing the exposure parameters of the adhesive layer, and the separation speed between the build platform and the vat after each layer. Moreover, high-precision scaffolds were successfully printed by adjusting contour offset, exposure energy, and exposure intensity. The as-printed scaffolds were subjected to debinding and sintering to obtain 1393B3 borate BG scaffolds. Observations under a stereomicroscope and scanning electron microscope (SEM) confirmed that the obtained scaffolds faithfully reproduced the complete structure and fine features of the original designs.

Keywords: 1393B3 borate bioactive glass, digital light processing, computer-aided design, bone-mimicking.

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The Effect of Nitrogen Incorporation of Alkali Free Bioactive Glasses

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ABSTRACT

Bioactive glasses (BG)s, like 45S5 Bioglass®, which consists of CaO, Na₂O, and P₂O₅ has gained interest owing to its ability of forming hydroxycarbonate apatite (HCA) layer in physiological fluids. However, due to its high Na₂O content (usually over 20 mol%) raises concerns about crystallization tendency and potential cytotoxicity with respect to rapid release of Na⁺ ions *in vitro* conditions. Alkali free, BGs have been developed to overcome these issues [1]. These glasses are expected to exhibit superior mechanical properties due to their more compact network structure and higher CaO content. Moreover, it is well established that the incorporation of nitrogen into glass networks enhances mechanical strength, primarily because nitrogen anions exhibit threefold coordination compared to the twofold coordination of oxygen anions[2]. In that regard, silicon nitride (Si₃N₄) is one of the promising additives owing to its biocompatibility, and osteointegrative potential [3]. Based on these considerations, this research investigates the structure-property correlation of Si₃N₄ doped alkali free BGs, First, alkali-free BG powders are melted in O₂ atmosphere at 1500–1550 °C, based on formulations from *Pablos-Martín* et al. [4]. Then, 90 wt.% of base BGs are mixed with 10 wt.% Si₃N₄ and re-melted at the same temperatures in an N₂ atmosphere. The resulting material will be examined through techniques such as X-ray diffraction, X-ray fluorescence, scanning electron microscopy, and differential thermal analysis.

Keywords: Alkali-free bioactive glasses, Mechanical properties, oxynitride glasses

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Bismuth-doped mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles with broad mesoporous distribution: physicochemical properties, bioactivity, and radiopacity

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ABSTRACT

Dendritic mesoporous bioactive glasses (DMBGs) are promising biomaterials due to their radial pore structure, broad mesoporous distribution, and high surface area, which support efficient loading and release of biomolecules. In this study, bismuth-doped DMBGs (Bi-DMBGs) were synthesised and characterised, with bismuth incorporated to provide radiopacity for clinical imaging and to impart reported antibacterial [1], photothermal [2], and angiogenic effects [3]. Mesoporous silica nanoparticles were prepared using a dual-surfactant sol-gel method, followed by sequential impregnation with calcium nitrate and a Bi-acetylacetonate complex in an acidic medium, and then calcination to yield compositions containing 0.5, 1, and 2 mol% Bi₂O₃. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) confirmed the silica network and near-complete surfactant removal, while inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) validated compositions close to the intended targets. X-ray diffraction (XRD) revealed an amorphous matrix without crystalline bismuth phases, indicating the dispersion of Bi within the glass network. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) revealed dendritic morphology, and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) showed homogeneous elemental distribution. Nitrogen sorption analysis using the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) model revealed broad mesoporosity with a high surface area and pore volume, which decreased with increasing Bi content but remained within the reported MBG ranges. In vitro assays in simulated body fluid (SBF) demonstrated sustained release of Si, Ca, and P, detection of Bi in doped samples, and apatite formation in all samples within 7 days, although a higher Bi content slightly delayed crystallisation. Radiopacity increased proportionally with Bi concentration. These findings demonstrate that Bi-DMBGs combine dendritic morphology, ion release, bioactivity, and radiopacity, making them promising candidates for bone regeneration applications.

Keywords: Mesoporous bioactive glass, dendritic, bismuth doping, bioactivity, radiopacity.

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Electrophoretic Deposition of Bismuth-Doped 1393-B3 Bioactive glass/PEEK Coating on Titanium implant for Biomedical Applications

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this project was to develop novel coating for Ti-based implants to enhance their bioactivity, improve biological responses, inhibit stress shielding, combat infection, and boost radiopacity. Borate bioactive glasses (BG) have been recently used in biomedical applications due to their rapid apatite ability formation in the physiological body fluids. 1393-B3 BG, in particular, with nominal composition in wt. % of 56.6 B₂O₃, 18.5 CaO, 11.1 K₂O, 5.5 Na₂O, 4.6 MgO, and 3.7 P₂O₅ is a highly bioactive borate BG that has recently attracted attention. Furthermore, incorporation of therapeutic ions is a common way to enhance the biological properties of BGs. In this study, Bi₂O₃ was aimed to be added to the 1393-B3 BG to enhance the potential radiopacity and antibacterial properties. Although BG-based coatings provide promising bioactivity, they usually exhibit a higher Young's modulus compared to bone, leading to stress shielding. They also show poor adhesion to the metal surfaces. In addition, they suffer from shrinkage issues during heat treatment. Therefore, it is preferable to composite them with other materials, like polymers, to overcome these limitations. Thus, polyether-ether-ketone (PEEK) with appropriate mechanical properties was incorporated alongside the BG to improve the adhesion and reduce stress shielding.

All BGs including 1393-B3 (Bi0) and Bi-doped BGs (Bi1, Bi2, and Bi3 with 5, 10, and 20 wt.% Bi₂O₃, respectively) were firstly synthesized and characterized through the melt-quenching technique. Then, PEEK/BG coatings were obtained via electrophoretic deposition (EPD) and were thermally treated at 350 °C subsequently in order to densification of BGs, crystallization of PEEK polymers, and enhancement of adhesion.

The indirect antibacterial assessment revealed that BG-containing coatings significantly inhibited the growth of both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria stains. The coating with Bi2 BGs indicated the best inhibition by more than 70 % reduction in the relative viability of the bacteria. The viability of MG-63 cells was also assessed in direct contact with the coatings after 2 days and 7 days of immersion. Although the results showed around 60 % of cells could survive on the surface of Bi-doped BG-based coatings, the fluorescent images showed the cells preferentially attached and spread on intact regions of the BG coating. The fold change (7 days/2 days) in BG-containing samples was close to Ti, suggesting comparable proliferation. Thus, the reduction in relative viability is not necessarily unfavourable and may reflect the effect of crack and surface topology. This is going to be checked via indirect test and the reduction in biocompatibility will be mitigated by surface modification in future studies.

Keywords: Borate glass, Bioactive glass, Bismuth, Electrophoretic deposition (EPD), Polyether-ether-ketone (PEEK), Ti implants.

3D-printed hydrogel scaffolds with bioactive glass and antibacterial propolis-loaded ZIF-8 for tissue regeneration

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ABSTRACT

Composite designing is crucial in tissue regeneration, where biomaterials aim to mimic the structure and properties of extracellular matrix (ECM). Hydrogel-bioactive glass (BG) composites are promising scaffolds as hydrogels provide high-water organic matrix similar to the target tissue and BG add bioactive functionality and reinforcement. Nevertheless, colonization of pathogens may result in infection, compromising the healing process. Therefore, giving antibacterial properties to these hydrogel scaffold became the spot of interest.

In this study, alginate dialdehyde-gelatin (ADA-GEL), a common hydrogel with suitable printability and biocompatibility was selected for 3D printing of BG-containing hydrogel scaffolds. Moreover, SiO₂-CaO BG nanoparticles were synthesised in spherical and uniform structure (~300 nm in diameter) were synthesized to endow the composite with bioactivity. Their apatite-forming ability after 7 days of immersion in the simulated body fluid (SBF) was confirmed by arising phosphorus-oxygen absorbance bond in Raman diagram and crystallized apatite peak in X-ray diffraction curve.

ZIF-8 particles, a Zn-based metal organic framework, was used as a carrier of antibacterial drug to introduce antibacterial functionality. On one hand, the extract of *propolis* as natural antimicrobial agent was selected to be incorporated into the ZIF-8 structure. On the other hand, ZIF-8 itself could sustainably release antibacterial Zn²⁺ ions, yielding synergistic antibacterial effects. *Propolis*-loaded ZIF-8 (ZP) particles was synthesized, and antibacterial assays demonstrated a significant inhibition of bacterial growth at 250 µg.mL⁻¹ concentration. The viability of *E. coli* and *S. aureus* bacteria was reduced to 32% and 2%, respectively. Furthermore, particles maintained their biocompatibility at this concentration, as confirmed by indirect cellular viability assays using MG-63 cells.

Eventually, scaffold was fabricated using both bioactive BG and antibacterial ZP particles in ADA-GEL hydrogel matrix. Both BG and ZP particles (0.2 % w/v each) were firstly dispersed in ADA solution (5% w/v) followed by the addition of GEL solution (7.5% w/v) to initiate Schiff's base reaction (in DPBS at 37 °C). The hydrogel scaffolds was obtained through 3D printing and then stabilized by post-crosslinking using CaCl₂ solution. Incorporation of both particles reduced hydrogel degradation in HBSS medium after 7 days from 27% to 9%. While BG and ZP particles are expected to provide bioactivity and antibacterial properties, further studies will evaluate. scaffold features in terms of cell viability and antibacterial effect.

Keywords: 3D printing, Antibacterial properties, Bioactive glass, Hydrogel, Metal-organic frameworks, ZIF-8.

Boron-Doped S53P4 Bioactive Glass-Ceramic Scaffolds Fabricated by LCD-masked Stereolithography for Bone Tissue Regeneration

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ABSTRACT

Scaffolds for bone tissue engineering must provide a 3D framework that supports cell attachment, proliferation, and tissue ingrowth while maintaining mechanical integrity. Achieving this balance requires an interconnected pore network with a suitable pore size, uniform interconnectivity, and controlled porosity. Stereolithography (SLA) additive manufacturing enables the fabrication of high-resolution architectures that mimic bone structure with precise geometric control. In this study, boron-doped S53P4-based (S53P4_10B) scaffolds were fabricated by LCD-masked stereolithography (MSLA) and evaluated for their structural, mechanical, and biological performance. An optimal slurry rheology was achieved with a low dispersant content, while viscosity increased markedly at higher solid loadings. SEM and thermal analysis revealed that S53P4_10B scaffolds (sintered at a lower temperature) achieved densification comparable to S53P4 scaffolds sintered at a higher temperature. XRD identified combeite and sodium borate as the main crystalline phases, with sodium borate contributing to accelerated dissolution and degradation kinetics. The S53P4_10B scaffolds exhibited higher compressive strength than S53P4 scaffolds, indicating boron-assisted densification at lower temperature. Among the scaffolds, only S53P4_10B demonstrated in vitro apatite formation, confirming its superior bioactivity, while both scaffolds maintained comparable cytocompatibility with MG-63 and ST-2 cells. Moreover, S53P4_10B scaffolds showed moderate antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, corresponding to their faster dissolution, observed by ICP-OES. Overall, boron incorporation enhances sintering behavior, mechanical performance, and biological functionality of MSLA-printed S53P4 scaffolds, demonstrating their potential as advanced biomaterials for bone tissue engineering.

Keywords: Bioactive glass, Boron, LCD-masked stereolithography, S53P4

Development of Scalable PFAS-Free Transparent Hydrophobic Film for Advanced Functional Surface Applications

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ABSTRACT

Automotive, architectural glass, and photovoltaic modules require hydrophobic coatings to have self-cleaning and anti-soiling properties. Traditional fluoropolymer coatings have been effective, but due to environmental and health concerns, the US and EU have been progressively limiting their use, creating demand for fluorine-free coatings that still offer transparency and water repellency [1]. One such alternative is 1,1,3,3-tetramethyldisiloxane (TMDSO), which forms favorable Si–C and Si–O bonding structure, enabling the formation of organosilicon networks with methyl (–CH₃) terminations responsible for hydrophobicity while maintaining optical transparency. Its compatibility with low-temperature PECVD processing and availability as a non-toxic, stable, and cost-effective precursor make it a promising alternative to fluorinated silanes.

In this work, fluorine-free hydrophobic thin films were developed using a linear hollow cathode plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) process with TMDSO as the precursor. A systematic optimization of deposition parameters including plasma power, TMDSO flow rate, and Ar/N₂ ratio was carried out to achieve maximum hydrophobicity while maintaining high transparency. The optimization aimed to retain surface –CH₃ groups, which govern hydrophobicity, while balancing plasma stability and film adhesion.

The coatings were analysed using UV–Vis spectroscopy to assess their transparency, thickness, and variation in refractive index. Surface wettability was measured using static contact angle tests. The optimized TMDSO coatings showed high transparency with hydrophobicity. Building upon our previously developed bilayer AR coatings (WAR = 3.26%, 3.6% efficiency gain over uncoated glass), the incorporation of this optimized TMDSO top layer imparts durable hydrophobic and anti-soiling functionality.

Keywords: PECVD, PVD, solar cells, antireflective coatings, hydrophobicity, TMDSO

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Optimising Alkali-Assisted Spray Drying for Additive Manufacturing of Glass-Ceramic Membranes

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on reusing and recycling ‘Fakulta Nemocnica Trenčín’ used hospital glass vials by repurposing them to develop photocatalytic glass-ceramic membranes for wastewater treatment. Additive manufacturing (AM) techniques in glass and ceramics offer benefits such as utilising recycled waste glass powder as raw material, better surface finish, design flexibility, control over porosity, and fewer surface defects. However, when recycled glass is used as a raw material, its irregular shape can impact resolution, cause layer adhesion issues, cracks, entrapment of carbon from resin, low packing density, and low mechanical strength.

This study prepared glass microspheres by optimising the slurry preparation parameters for spray drying. The study aims to use alkaline solutions – NaOH and KOH- as binders during spray drying, enabling the formation of surface interfacial bonds between TiO₂ and waste glass powder. To assess the alkali effect on forming composite glass microspheres, three different preparation routes (based on mixing methods) were designed: i) mechanical mixing of glass powder and TiO₂ in alkali solutions, ii) a hybrid approach combining mechanical mixing and ball milling of alkali solutions with binders and glass-TiO₂ composites, and iii) ball milling of alkali solutions, binders, and glass-TiO₂ composites.

The morphology of the resulting microspheres was analysed using SEM and particle size analysis. The optimal preparation route was chosen based on the spherical morphology achieved through the binding and mixing process. During additive manufacturing, the samples were heated in a muffle furnace to improve their strength and enhance the stability of spray-dried particles as precursor powder. Therefore, this study highlights spray drying to produce spherical granules at low temperature from waste glass as a precursor powder with uniform morphology for AM, such as Digital Light Processing (DLP) [1], and Direct Ink Writing to print membranes.

Keywords: Recycling waste glass, alkaline activation, spray drying, flame synthesis, photocatalysis, wastewater treatment, 3D design and printing.

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Wear Mechanisms of Fused-Cast AZS Glass Tank Refractories During Dissolution in Barium Cristallin Glass

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ABSTRACT

Fused-cast $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2\text{-SiO}_2$ (AZS) refractories are widely used in glass furnaces because of their exceptional corrosion resistance and thermal stability. However, prolonged exposure to molten barium cristallin glass leads to significant degradation, reducing furnace service life and operational efficiency. With the glass industry's ongoing shift toward electric and hybrid-electric melting technologies for decarbonization, understanding of refractory performance has become increasingly important, as these systems introduce distinct thermal profiles and chemical environments that influence corrosion behavior. This study investigated the phase evolution and wear behavior of various AZS refractory compositions through a combined computational and experimental approach. Simultaneous thermal analysis was conducted and especially the differential scanning calorimetric thermogram was utilized to determine the glass transition temperature and further the nucleation temperature of the glassy phase present in the AZS refractories. Thermodynamic simulations using FactSage were used to predict phase equilibrium over a temperature range and determine the temperature range where mullite is stable. These predictions were experimentally validated through controlled tempering of the samples and subsequent X-ray diffraction analysis with internal standard to quantify the phases including the amorphous using Rietveld refinement. Mullite formation was evaluated by SEM-EDS analysis. Dynamic corrosion tests were performed using a continuous wear testing device at 200 rpm to simulate industrial glass flow and assess dissolution and erosion under forced convection. The combined results establish links between phase formation, microstructural evolution, and corrosion resistance. These findings contribute to optimizing AZS refractory performance for both conventional and emerging electric melting technologies.

Keywords: AZS refractories; glass tanks; barium cristallin glass; mullite formation; refractory wear.

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Feasibility Study on the Upcycling of Waste Soda-Lime Glass into Structural 3D Glass-Ceramic Components using Binder Jetting Technology

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ABSTRACT

The accumulation of waste glass poses a major environmental challenge due to its non-biodegradable nature and low recycling rates. The recycling rate remains low primarily because of contamination, color mixing, and breakage during collection. To address this issue, the present study explores the feasibility of upcycling waste soda-lime glass into structural glass-ceramic parts using binder jetting additive manufacturing. This work employs two key advantages of binder jetting; i) large-scale manufacturing capability and, ii) its potential to maximize waste glass utilization to develop sustainable glass-ceramic components.

Waste soda-lime glass obtained from discarded chemical containers provided by CENTRALCHEM, s.r.o., (Slovakia) was milled to a particle size below 125 μm and used to prepare feedstock for binder jetting. XRF analysis confirmed the chemical composition of the soda-lime glass. Thermal analysis (TG–DTA) indicated a glass transition temperature around 560 °C, while hot-stage microscopy (HSM) showed viscous collapse above 700 °C. To enhance thermal stability, the composition was modified by incorporating unrecyclable waste fibre glass in a 60:40 ratio to investigate how the combined composition influences the properties of the resulting material. The modified composition retained its shape up to 1000 °C, demonstrating improved stability suitable for structural applications. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis further confirmed the presence of distinct mechanically reinforcing crystalline phases, mainly β -wollastonite, in the sintered parts, validating the successful transformation of the glass matrix into a glass-ceramic structure. The preliminary results demonstrate that binder jetting can effectively upcycle mixed waste glass systems into structurally stable and thermally stable glass-ceramic components.

Keywords: Binder jetting, Glass-ceramic components, Fibre glass, Soda-lime glass, Up-cycling.

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Understanding the capacitive and diffusion controlled behavior of brown mud 3D printed electrode in different electrolyte medium.

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we report the successful fabrication of three-dimensional (3D) oxide electrodes through additive manufacturing techniques, i.e., fused deposition modeling (FDM). The red/brown mud, an iron oxide-rich byproduct of aluminum refining, which is highly alkaline in nature, will be employed as the primary catalyst material. Subsequently, the industrial brown mud and polylactic acid (PLA) binders of varying compositions will be incorporated to form brown mud filaments. This prepared filament will be directly utilized for FDM to print the working electrodes. The printed electrodes were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis to determine their structural and surface features. Electrochemical study will be carried out in different electrolyte solutions, to reveal the distinct capacitive and diffusive charge storage mechanisms. Furthermore, field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) analysis will be done to study the 3D electrodes structural integrity and surface architecture in various electrolyte solutions. The prepared 3D electrode will be used in a three-electrode setup to study electrochemical double-layer capacitance (EDLC). This research offers a sustainable pathway for upcycling industrial waste into functional electrodes for energy conversion and storage applications.

Keywords: energy conversion, fused deposition modeling, supercapacitance, polylactic acid (PLA), upcycling of waste, and supercapacitors.

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